

Neuroethics in the Human Brain Project

A collection of articles in academic journals and publicity for our work

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1. Introduction

This is a collection of articles in academic journals and publicity for our work on neuroethics in the Human Brain Project from April 2020 to September 2023 (SGA3). The report is an official output (9.12) from the work package on responsible research and innovation, listing articles on neuroethics in academic journals, and articles and interviews in public media on neuroethics and engagement with citizens, through two research blogs: The Human Brain Projects own blog Ethics Dialogues (www.ethicsdialogues.eu) and Uppsala University's Ethics Blog (www.ethicsblog.crb.uu.se). The research received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under the Specific Grant Agreement No. HBP SGA3.

The legacy of the entire decade of work on Neuroethics and the Human Brain Project can be accessed in our [report on social, ethical & reflective work in the Human Brain Project](#), listing all scientific publications contributing to responsible neuroscience in the Human Brain Project. Neuroethics is also a part of the [online training resources on responsible research and innovation](#), covering a wide range of issues that can all be accessed on the Human Brain Project Website. It is also part of an [Ethics & Society Toolkit](#) with tools for reflecting on ethical and socially responsible practices in brain research.

2. Scientific publications

All publications on ethical, social and reflective work in the Human Brain Project has been summarised in a report listing of all articles, books, and reports produced since the beginning of the Human Brain Project in October 2013. The report was first published in October of 2021, and updated in March 2023, and is [available for download on the Zenodo platform](#). The report will be updated again in September 2023, as part of OP9.10. Cite the report as: HBP SP12 and WP9. (2021). Social, ethical & reflective work in the Human Brain Project (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7763281>.

2.1 Ethics & Society Anthology

Bitsch, L., Salles, A., Evers, K., Changeux, J-P., Stahl, B, Aicardi, C., Burton Datta, S., Mahfoud, T., Reinsborough, M., Rose, N., Klüver, L., Ladegaard, S.F., Alves, E., Nordfalk, F., Bådum, N., Eke, D., Knight, W., Grasenick, K., Romero, P.F., Ulnicane, I., Rosemann, A., Ogoh, G., Matar, A., Fernow, J., Bringedal, B., Christen, M., Domingo-Ferrer, J., von Schomberg, R., Illes, J., Rommelfanger, K. (2023). Ethics and Society in Brain Research: Implementing Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in the Human Brain Project (HBP). Zenodo. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7736402](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7736402)

2.2 Opinions and Action Papers

Aicardi, C., Bitsch, L., Datta Burton, S., Evers, K., Farisco, M., Mahfoud, T., Rose, N., Rosemann, A., Salles, A., Stahl, B., Ulnicane, I. Opinion on Trust and Transparency in Artificial Intelligence (2021) Ethics and Society, The Human Brain Project. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.4588648](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4588648)

Aicardi, C., Bitsch, L., B. Bådum, N., Datta, S., Evers, K., Fothergill, T., Giordano, J., Harris, E., Jørgensen, M.L, Klüver, L., Mahfoud, T., Rainey, S., Riisgaard, K., Rose, N., Salles, A., Stahl, B., Ulnicane, I. Opinion on 'Responsible Dual Use'- Political, Security, Intelligence and Military Research

of Concern in Neuroscience and Neurotechnology (2018), Ethics and Society, The Human Brain Project. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.4588601](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4588601)

Salles, A., Stahl, B., Bjaalie, J., Domingo-Ferrer, J., Rose, N., Rainey S., Spranger, T. Opinion and Action Plan on 'Data Protection and Privacy (2017) Ethics and Society, The Human Brain Project. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.4588467](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4588467)

2.3 Peer Reviewed Articles

Farisco, M., Formisano, R., Gosseries, O., Kato, Y., Koboyashi, S., Laureys, S., Lejeune, N., Martial, C., Matar, Amal., Morrisey, A-M., Schnakers, C., Yakufujiang, M., Yamaki, T., Veeramuthu, V., Zandalasini, M., Zasler, N., Magliacano, A., Estraneo, A. International survey on the implementation of the European and American guidelines on disorders of consciousness. *Journal of Neurology*. (In press)

Farisco, M., Baldassarre, G., Cartoni, E., Leach, A., Petrovici, M.A., Rosemann, A., Salles, A., Stahl, B., van Albada, S. J. A method for the ethical analysis of brain-inspired AI, (2023) arXiv:2305.10938 doi: [10.48550/arXiv.2305.10938](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.10938)

Sallin, K., Evers, K., Jarbin, H. *et al.* Separation and not residency permit restores function in resignation syndrome: a retrospective cohort study. *Eur Child Adolesc Psychiatry* 32, 75-86 (2023). Doi: [10.1007/s00787-021-01833-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-021-01833-3)

Farisco, M (2023) The Ethical Spectrum of Consciousness, *AJOB Neuroscience*, 14:2, 55-57, doi: [10.1080/21507740.2023.2188312](https://doi.org/10.1080/21507740.2023.2188312)

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Schnakers, C., Bauer, C., Formisano, R., Noé, E., Llorens, R., Lejeune, N., Farisco, M., Teixeira, L., Morrissey, A-M., De Marco, S., Veeramuthu, V., Ilina, K., Edlow, BL., Gosseries, O., Zandalasini, M., De Bellis, F., Thibaut, A., Estraneo, A. (2022) What names for covert awareness? A systematic review. Front. Hum. Neurosci. 16:971315. doi: [10.3389/fnhum.2022.971315](https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2022.971315)

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2.4 Books and Book Chapters

M. Farisco, The ethical implications of indicators of consciousness in artificial system, in G. Stark, M. Ienca (eds.), *Brains and Machines: Towards a unified Ethics of AI and Neuroscience*, Elsevier (In Press).

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Salles, A. (2023). Some reflections on the neurorights debate. In: *The risks and challenges of neurotechnologies for human rights*. Eds Sosa Navarro, M., Salvador Dura-Bernal, C. M. G. (UNESCO, University of Milan-Bicocca, SUNY Downstate). ISBN 978-92-3-100567-1

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Evers, K. (2013) Neuroethics, in *Encyclopedia of Sciences and Religions*, Springer Science + Business Media B.V., Dordrecht 2013: 1466-1471, doi: [10.1007/978-1-4020-8265-8_1529](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8265-8_1529)

2.5 HBP Reports

Evers, K., Farisco, M., Giordano, J., Salles, A. (2017) Dual Use in Neuroscientific and Neurotechnological Research. A Report on Background, Developments and Recommendations for Ethical Address, Assessment and Guidance of Human Brain Project Activities. HBP Neuroethics and Philosophy (SP-12) CRB-Uppsala University Report

Dudai, Y., Evers, K., Second report on simulation, brain, body and environment (2016), the Human Brain Project

Dudai, Y., Evers, K. (2015) First report on how far brain simulation can explain mechanisms of the mind, the Human Brain Project

3. Dissertations

Farisco, M. (2019) Brain, Consciousness and Disorders of Consciousness at the Intersection of Neuroscience and Philosophy. Digital Comprehensive Summaries of Uppsala Dissertations from the Faculty of Medicine 1597 (63 pp). Uppsala: Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis ISBN 978-91-513-0749-7 <http://uu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1347252/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

4. Neuroethics on the Ethics Blog

Uppsala University's Ethics Blog (etihsblog.crb.uu.se) reaches over 7,500 e-mail subscribers through its English and Swedish language blog platforms, in addition to direct hits on the website and clicks on content posted on Twitter, where the blog posts directly to , with relevant posts also shared on the HBP & Society twitter handle: <https://twitter.com/HBPSociety>.

Between April 2020 and September 2023, the Ethics Blog published 84 texts on Neuroethics, authored by Pär Segerdahl, Michele Farisco & Josepine Fernow. This represents 42 original texts in English, with the number of posts doubling for a Swedish language audience on www.etikbloggen.crb.uu.se, where full Swedish language versions of texts by Pär Segerdahl and Josepine Fernow have been published, and short introductions to texts by Michele Farisco (authored by Pär Segerdahl) have been posted, linking to the full text in English. Below a list of blog posts in English.

30 May 2023, Pär Segerdahl:

Encourage children to take responsibility for others?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2023/05/30/encourage-children-to-take-responsibility-for-others/>

16 May 2023, Pär Segerdahl:

When ordinary words get scientific uses

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2023/05/16/when-ordinary-words-get-scientific-uses/>

25 April 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Taking care of the legacy: curating responsible research and innovation practice

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2023/04/25/taking-care-of-the-legacy-curating-responsible-research-and-innovation-practice/>

21 March 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Science, science communication and language

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2023/03/21/science-science-communication-and-language/>

28 February 2023, Michele Farisco:

A new project will explore the prospect of artificial awareness

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2023/02/28/a-new-project-will-explore-the-prospect-of-artificial-awareness/>

8 November 2022, Pär Segerdahl:

A charming idea about consciousness

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/11/08/a-charming-idea-about-consciousness/>

25 October 2022, Josepine Fernow:

AI narratives from the Global North

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/10/25/ai-narratives-from-the-global-north/>

4 October 2022, Pär Segerdahl:

Does the brain make room for free will?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/10/04/does-the-brain-make-room-for-free-will/>

20 September 2022, Pär Segerdahl:

Artificial intelligence: augmenting intelligence in humans or creating human intelligence in machines?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/09/20/artificial-intelligence-augmenting-intelligence-in-humans-or-creating-human-intelligence-in-machines/>

31 May 2022, Michele Farisco:

An ethical strategy for improving the healthcare of brain-damaged patients

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/05/31/an-ethical-strategy-for-improving-the-healthcare-of-brain-damaged-patients/>

19 April 2022, Michele Farisco:

How can we detect consciousness in brain-damaged patients?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/04/19/how-can-we-detect-consciousness-in-brain-damaged-patients/>

22 March 2022, Pär Segerdahl:

Fact resistance, human nature and contemplation

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/03/22/fact-resistance-and-contemplation/>

8 March 2022, Michele Farisco:

How can neuroethics and AI ethics join their forces?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/03/08/how-can-neuroethics-and-ai-ethics-join-their-forces/>

15 February 2022, Pär Segerdahl:

Images of good and evil artificial intelligence

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/02/15/images-of-good-and-evil-artificial-intelligence/>

18 January 2022, Pär Segerdahl:

Digital twins, virtual brains and the dangers of language

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2022/01/18/digital-twins-virtual-brains-and-the-dangers-of-language/>

21 December 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Inspired

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/12/21/inspired/>

14 December 2021, Michele Farisco:

Brain-inspired AI: human narcissism again?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/12/14/brain-inspired-ai-human-narcissism-again/>

16 November 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Conceptual analysis when we get stuck in thoughts

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/11/16/conceptual-analysis-when-we-get-stuck-in-thoughts/>

26 October 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Philosophical research communication

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/10/26/philosophical-research-communication/>

19 October 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Neuroimaging the brain without revealing the person

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/10/19/neuroimaging-the-brain-without-revealing-the-person/>

21 September 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Securing the future already from the beginning

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/09/21/securing-the-future-already-from-the-beginning/>

1 September 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Can subjectivity be explained objectively?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/09/01/can-subjectivity-be-explained-objectively/>

13 July 2021, Michele Farisco:

Consciousness and complexity: theoretical challenges for a practically useful idea

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/07/13/consciousness-and-complexity-theoretical-challenges-for-a-practically-useful-idea/>

1 June 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

To change the changing human

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/06/01/to-change-the-changing-human/>

11 May 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Can you be cloned?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/05/11/can-you-be-cloned/>

4 May 2021, Michele Farisco:

Can AI be conscious? Let us think about the question

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/05/04/can-ai-be-conscious-let-us-think-about-the-question/>

20 April 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

An unusually big question

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/04/20/an-unusually-big-question/>

9 March 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Human rights and legal issues related to artificial intelligence

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/03/09/human-rights-and-legal-issues-related-to-artificial-intelligence/>

2 March 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Learning from international attempts to legislate psychosurgery

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/03/02/learning-from-international-attempts-to-legislate-psychosurgery/>

9 February 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

How do we take responsibility for dual-use research?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/02/09/how-do-we-take-responsibility-for-dual-use-research/>

26 January 2021, Michele Farisco:

The hard problem of consciousness: please handle with care!

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/01/26/the-hard-problem-of-consciousness-please-handle-with-care/>

12 January 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Threatened by superintelligent machines

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2021/01/12/threatened-by-superintelligent-machines/>

1 December 2020, Michele Farisco:

Are you conscious? Looking for reliable indicators

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/12/01/are-you-conscious-looking-for-reliable-indicators/>

18 November 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

Ethically responsible robot development

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/11/18/ethically-responsible-robot-development/>

26 October 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

“Cooperative,” “pleasant” and “reliable” robot colleague is wanted

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/10/26/cooperative-pleasant-and-reliable-robot-colleague-is-wanted/>

5 October 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

We shape the societies that shape us: our responsibility for human nature

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/10/05/we-shape-the-societies-that-shape-us-our-responsibility-for-human-nature/>

14 September 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

What is required of an ethics of artificial intelligence?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/09/14/what-is-required-of-the-ethics-of-artificial-intelligence/>

26 August 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

Ethics as renewed clarity about new situations

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/08/26/ethics-as-renewed-clarity-about-new-situations/>

19 August 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

Ethical frameworks for research

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/08/19/ethical-frameworks-for-research/>

27 July 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

Working online during the pandemic: recommendations from the Human Brain Project

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/07/27/working-online-during-the-pandemic-recommendations-from-the-human-brain-project/>

23 June 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

Ethical fitness apps for high performance morality

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/06/23/ethical-fitness-apps-for-high-performance-morality/>

25 May 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

Responsibly planned research communication

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/05/25/responsibly-planned-research-communication/>

27 April 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

Inspiration for responsible research and innovation

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/04/27/inspiration-for-responsible-research-and-innovation/>

15 April 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

Anthropomorphism in AI can limit scientific and technological development

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/04/15/anthropomorphism-in-ai-can-limit-scientific-and-technological-development/>

1 April 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

What is a moral machine?

<https://ethicsblog.crb.uu.se/2020/04/01/what-is-a-moral-machine/>

5. Neuroethics on Ethics Dialogues

Between April 2020 and September 2023, the Ethics Dialogues blog has played an important role as a platform for sharing information about the social, ethical and reflective work in the Human Brain project. However, for the neuroethics audience, Ethics Dialogues has served as a complement to the Uppsala University Ethics Blog, with an audience of close to 8,000 e-mail subscribers. In the beginning of 2020, some posts from the Uppsala University Ethics Blog were cross-posted on Ethics Dialogues. After evaluation of the reach, this strategy was abandoned in favour of the Ethics Blog. Using Ethics Dialogues to disseminate more editorial or plain language summaries of key messages from publications, in many cases, these texts have been reposted on the Human Brain Project's news feed, and posted to the Ethics & Society Twitter/X handle: <https://twitter.com/HBPSociety>.

Between April 2020 and September 2023, Ethics Dialogues published 27 texts categorised or tagged with Neuroethics, authored by Josepine Fernow, Anna Holm, Pär Segerdahl, Michele Farisco, Lise Bitsch, Inga Ulnicane, Arleen Salles & Märta Karlén.

17 August 2023, Anna Holm:

Identify, assess and better manage ethical issues raised by brain research!

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/08/17/identify-assess-and-better-manage-ethical-issues-raised-by-brain-research/>

10 August 2023, Lise Bitsch, Josepine Fernow:

Including society and ethics in brain science

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/08/10/including-society-and-ethics-in-brain-science/>

22 June 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Measuring & describing consciousness: clinical tool and theoretical model prove compatible

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/06/21/measuring-and-describing-consciousness/>

22 May 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Time to move from 'AI Ethics' to a notion of responsible AI ecosystems

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/05/22/time-to-move-from-ai-ethics-to-a-notion-of-responsible-ai-ecosystems/>

2 May 2023, Märta Karlén:

Building capacity for responsible brain research and innovation

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/05/02/building-capacity-for-responsible-brain-research-and-innovation/>

26 April 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Emerging ethical issues in research on consciousness

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/04/26/emerging-ethical-issues-in-research-on-consciousness/>

12 April 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Implementing responsible research and innovation in the Human Brain Project

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/04/12/implementing-responsible-research-and-innovation-in-the-human-brain-project/>

3 April 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Time to rethink the AI ethics narrative

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/04/03/time-to-rethink-the-ai-ethics-narrative/>

24 Mars 2023, Josepine Fernow:

First systematic review of Artificial Intelligence impact assessments

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/03/24/first-systematic-review-of-artificial-intelligence-impact-assessments/>

21 Mars 2023, Lise Bitsch, Inga Ulnicane & Arleen Salles:

The future of Responsible Brain Research

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/03/21/the-future-of-responsible-brain-research/>

13 Mars 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Curating the legacy of responsible research and innovation in the Human Brain Project

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/03/13/curating-the-legacy-of-responsible-research-and-innovation-in-the-human-brain-project/>

13 February 2023, Josepine Fernow:

Broadening the debate on neurorights

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2023/02/13/broadening-the-debate-on-neurorights/>

14 April 2022, Anna Holm:

Responsibility key to implementing guidelines for treating disorders of consciousness

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2022/04/14/responsibility-key-to-implementing-guidelines-for-treating-disorders-of-consciousness/>

23 Mars 2022, Anna Holm:

Indicators and criteria of consciousness for behaviourally unresponsive patients

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2022/03/23/indicators-and-criteria-of-consciousness-for-behaviourally-unresponsive-patients/>

4 February 2022, Anna Holm:

The neuroethics contribution to AI ethics regulation

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2022/02/04/the-neuroethics-contribution-to-ai-ethics-and-regulation/>

3 February 2022, Michele Farisco:

Calling all professionals working with Disorders of Consciousness!

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2022/02/03/calling-all-professionals-working-with-disorders-of-consciousness/>

22 December 2021, Michele Farisco:

Are you conscious? Looking for reliable indicators

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2020/12/22/are-you-conscious-looking-for-reliable-indicators/>

14 December 2021, Anna Holm:

Digital twins & virtual brains: the importance of conceptual clarity and transparency

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2021/12/14/digital-twins-virtual-brains-the-importance-of-conceptual-clarity-and-transparency/>

13 December 2021, Josepine Fernow:

The value of neuroethics and philosophical reflection in the Human Brain Project

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2021/12/13/the-value-of-neuroethics-and-philosophical-reflection-in-the-human-brain-project/>

20 July 2021, Pär Segerdahl:

Can you be cloned?

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2021/07/20/can-you-be-cloned/>

13 July 2021, Michele Farisco:

Can AI be conscious? Let us think about the question

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2021/07/13/can-ai-be-conscious-let-us-think-about-the-question/>

17 February 2021, Michele Farisco:

The hard problem of consciousness: please handle with care!

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2021/02/17/the-hard-problem-of-consciousness-please-handle-with-care/>

12 October 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

We shape the societies that shape us: our responsibility for human nature

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2020/10/12/we-shape-the-societies-that-shape-us-our-responsibility-for-human-nature/>

29 September 2020, Anna Holm:

Culturally shaping developing minds

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2020/09/29/culturally-shaping-developing-minds/>

23 September 2020, Anna Holm:

Space, time: bridging the epistemic gap of brain & mind

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2020/09/23/space-time-bridging-the-epistemic-gap-of-brain-mind/>

17 September 2020, Pär Segerdahl:

What is required of an ethics of artificial intelligence?

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2020/09/17/what-is-required-of-an-ethics-of-artificial-intelligence/>

17 August 2020, Josepine Fernow:

Paper roundup - Neuroethics, AI ethics, dual-use, responsible neurorobotics & how to carry on during the Covid-19 crisis

<https://www.ethicsdialogues.eu/2020/08/17/paper-roundup-neuroethics-ai-ethics-dual-use-responsible-neurorobotics-how-to-carry-on-during-the-covid-19-crisis/>

6. Media coverage

15 February 2022, Manuel Guerrero:

[The Quest to Make a Digital Replica of Your Brain](#), Wired, 2022-02-15

4 May 2021, Kathinka Evers:

The identity of clones and what it tells us about the self, [I cannot be cloned](#), iai news, 2021-05-04

26 December 2021, Michele Farisco

[Der dunkle Geist - Vorstoß ins unbewusste Bewusstsein](#), Deutschlandfunk, 2021-12-26

20 February 2023, Arleen Salles:

HBP Podcast [Ep.4 - The Ethics of Brain Research: A conversation with Arleen Salles](#), Human Brain Project podcast

Karl Sallin, PhD student at Uppsala University received a lot of attention for a publication in 2021 that will form part of his thesis. He has also been interviewed in Swedish media on several occasions, providing expertise on pervasive refusal syndrome. Below a list of media coverage:

- [Pappa fick över en miljon för att vårda sin apatiska dotter](#)
Expressen, 2022-01-03
- [Apatiska barn blev friska när de vårdades ensamma](#)
forskning.se, 26 October 2021
- [Rön på tvärs med råd för apatiska barn](#)
Aftonbladet, 21 October 2021
- [Ny studie: Apatiska barn tillfrisknade när familjen avlägsnades](#)
Bulletin, 21 October 2021
- [Ny studie väcker frågetecken om råd till "apatiska barn"](#)
P4 Uppland, 21 October 2021
- [Rön på tvärs med råd för apatiska barn](#)
Göteborgsposten, 21 October 2021
- [Studie motsäger Socialstyrelsens tidigare råd kring uppgivenhetssyndrom](#)
SVT Nyheter, 21 October 2021
- [Ny forskning: Apatiska barn blev friska utan familjen](#)
Uppsala Nya Tidning, 21 October 2021
- [Decoding a Disorder at the Interface of Mind and Brain](#)
Uppsala Scientific American, 1 November